

PRINCIPAL'S LEADERSHIP IN FOSTERING A LITERACY CULTURE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN INDRAMAYU DISTRICT (QUALITATIVE RESEARCH ON YAPIN SMA KERTASEMAYA, INDRAMAYU REGENCY)

R. SUPYAN SAURI

Email: uyunsupyan@uninus.ac.id

EPING

Email: eping_s2adm_19@uninus.ac.id

NURJAMAN

Email: nurjaman_s2adm_19@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

The background of this research problem refers to the results of the 2018 Reading Literacy Activity Index (Alibaca Index) study conducted by the Policy Research Center Study Team. This study concludes that the National Alibaca Index is included in the category of low literacy activity with 37.32 points. The purpose of the study was to get an overview and analyze the Principal's Leadership in Fostering a Literacy Culture for High School Students in Indramayu Regency. The research procedure uses a qualitative approach with analytical descriptive methods, with the locus of SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya Indramayu Regency, which is used as a resource for School Supervisors, Principals, Teachers and Students. The theoretical basis used is the management theory of G. Terry and is supported by the School Literacy Movement Program Policy (GLS) to strengthen the character development movement as stated in the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015 concerning the Growth of Character. Research result The Principal's Leadership in Fostering a Literacy Culture of High School Students in Indramayu Regency, has been going quite well, in accordance with management rules that begin with planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating, but has not shown comprehensive performance, because the level of understanding of the School Literacy Movement program has not equally. Other aspects that become obstacles include librarians who are not yet professional, the availability of library collections is not complete, and the corner of the reading room is not comfortable, funding needs to be increased.

Key words: leadership, culture, literacy.

Introduction

Basic literacy consisting of literacy, numeracy, science, digital, finance, culture and citizenship is part of 21st century skills. Along with competence and character, these three things will lead to lifelong learning. The Government's response is to issue a School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) policy to strengthen the character development movement as stated in the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015 concerning Character Development. One of the activities in the movement is "a 15-minute activity of reading non-lesson books before study time begins". This activity is carried out to foster student interest in reading and improve reading skills so that knowledge can be mastered better. The reading

material contains moral values, in the form of local, national, and global wisdom that is delivered according to the stage of development of students. The ability to read must be owned by everyone, especially school children. Because by reading children can have the knowledge and ability to think broadly and are able to learn various fields of study, therefore reading is a skill that must be familiarized and taught when entering formal school for the first time. Meanwhile, the issuance of Ministerial Regulation number 23 of 2015 developed the School Literacy Movement which furthermore was to foster a noble attitude of character towards children through language and is an effort so that all school members and the community are always accustomed to socializing with each other based on character values.

Referring to the 2018 PISA report released by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) it shows the ability of Indonesian students to read, achieving an average score of 371, with an average OECD score of 487. Then for the average math score reaching 379 with an OECD average score of 487. Furthermore, for science, the average score of Indonesian students reached 389 with an OECD average score of 489. These data still reflect that educational institutions in Indonesia have not been optimal in accommodating students' learning interests, especially reading and writing. As a learning need.

Paying attention to the results of the 2018 Reading Literacy Activity Index (Alibaca Index) study conducted by the Policy Research Center Study Team. This study concludes that the National Alibaca Index is included in the category of low literacy activity with 37.32 points. When viewed at the provincial level, as many as 9 provinces are in the medium category; 14 provinces are categorized as low; and 1 province is very low. This means that most provinces are at a low level of literacy activity and none of the provinces are included in a high level of literacy activity (Solihin, et al., 2019).

Following up on the findings of PISA in 2009 the government through the Minister of Education issued Permendikbud Number 21 of 2015 concerning the School Literacy Movement. In simple terms, literacy can be interpreted as an ability to read and write (Jaka Warsihna. 2016) The school literacy movement is an effort so that the educational environment can carry out literacy activities on various opportunities both at school and at home. Through GLS, libraries are encouraged to be at the forefront of growing literacy activities. The response to the GLS policy was followed up by the Regional Government of Indramayu Regency issuing Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2018 concerning the Indramayu Reading Development Movement (Gerbang Maca) as a form of concern in implementing literacy activities. One of the important points of the regulation is to encourage reading 15 minutes before studying.

The strategic environment of the educational unit or school organization is heavily influenced by the professional leadership activities of the principal. Attributes inherent in school leadership must always be creative and productive in carrying out educational innovations to improve the quality of education (Danu Mihardja: 2001: 39). To improve the professionalism of principals in educational institutions, various efforts are needed in the form of increasing work creativity, work motivation, performance and work productivity of principals, on an ongoing basis by involving stakeholders.

Viewed from the aspect of national policy, education is a conscious effort made by humans to rationalize all aspects and potentials that exist within themselves and are carried out throughout their lives, which are carried out at various loci of human life, both in the family, school and community environment. According to M. Arifin (2003:15) Education is also a cultural process to improve human dignity in society.

The school is an organization in which the transformation of knowledge, attitudes and skills takes place from teachers to students. In practice, school principals need to have the ability to create a conducive teaching and learning situation, so that the school environment can carry out learning well and students can learn in peace (Hasrat A. Aimang, 20190). Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture (Permendikbud) No. 6 of 2019 concerning the Organizational Structure of Schools that there must be at least 3 components in the school including the principal, functional position group and implementing position group. In addition to the three main elements, there are other supporting elements including the administration, deputy head of curriculum, deputy head of student affairs, deputy head of infrastructure and deputy head of public relations in which there are sub-sectors of positions that are interrelated in terms of performance.

Permendikbud 6 of 2018 concerning Assignment of Teachers as Principals states that the principal is the leader who regulates and manages the school. In addition, the principal is the father and mother of all personnel in the school. This implies that the implementation of school activities depends a lot on the quality of its leadership. Permendikbud Number 13 of 2007 concerning Standards for Principals that school principals must have qualification and competency standards. The principal must have leadership qualities that are more than all personnel in the school. Some of the criteria that must be possessed include a problem solver, being positive, communicative, inspiring, motivating, having good relations, and having to be an example.

Principal leadership is the ability and authority to influence, move and direct actions and encourage the emergence of a strong will with enthusiasm and confidence for teachers, staff and students in carrying out their respective tasks for progress and inspire schools in achieving goals.

Culture is a way of life that develops and is owned by a group of people, and is passed down from generation to generation. Culture is defined as an activity that is carried out continuously and consistently. Literacy culture cannot be separated from the concept of education to reconstruct the next generation. The school literacy movement aims to familiarize students with reading and writing in order to cultivate character. (Silvia Sandi Graduation Lubis (2020). Every element in the school from the principal, teachers and students is required to master literacy competencies.

Literacy culture in the school environment must be developed by principals and teachers as inspirational subjects and motivators by their students. Principals and teachers must have literacy competencies which are then made a habit by their students. In simple terms, literacy culture is defined as an activity that is carried out continuously in the process of human life in

the form of reading skills, numeracy, and scientific literacy, digital, financial and living in a state.

From the description of the literacy problem above, it is very important to conduct research, with the aim of describing and analyzing the Principal's Leadership in Developing a Literacy Culture for High School Students in Indramayu Regency, in this study using a qualitative approach. The theoretical basis used is the theory of leadership and the theory of cultural literacy.

Research methods

This research is motivated by the results of studies and reports that measure reading, math, and science skills. Scores for reading, math, and science were 371, 379, and 376, respectively. This is below the OECD average. Specifically for reading, there are 70% of students whose abilities are below the minimum competence (Puspendik, 2018). The purpose of the study was to describe and analyze the planning, organization, implementation and evaluation of the school literacy movement at SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya, Indramayu Regency. This study uses a qualitative approach with analytical descriptive methods, the research is carried out from February 2, 2022 to June 15, 2022. The theoretical basis used is Management from G. Terry. The data collected in the implementation of this research is in the form of qualitative data originating from the data collection process using triangulation techniques, namely observation or observation, documentation studies and in-depth interviews. The data collection instrument is equipped with a research grid, observation guide or observation, documentation studies and interviews, the researchers themselves as the main instrument directly involved in extracting information. The research subjects were School Supervisors, Principals, Deputy Principals and Teachers. The criteria used in improving and determining the validity of the data, namely the degree of trust (credibility), transferability (transferability), dependence (defendability), and certainty (confirmability). The validity of the data was tested by using triangulation techniques and triangulation of data sources. Data analysis uses a qualitative model which includes data collection, data reduction and display, and conclusion drawing.

Results and Discussion

YAPIN Kertasemaya High School has its address at Jalan Raya Tulungagung No.76 Kertasemaya, Tulungagung, Jatibarang District, Indramayu Regency, and West Java 66292. The reason for this study is because the school has implemented the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS). Based on the results of observations, in-depth interviews and documentation studies on management aspects of the School Literacy Movement (GLS):

a. Dimensions of planning for the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) at SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya Indramayu:

Beginning with the formation of the Drafting Team for the revitalization of the School's Vision, Mission, Goals and Strategy, which involves all elements in the school environment, such as school supervisors, school committees, teachers. The VMTS formulation made by TIM was

held in seminars by inviting experts from universities. Then it was decided by the Principal, namely ADIL Vision, Active in positive activities, High dedication in shaping the nation's character, High innovation towards the times, Straightforward in real work.

The next step is to formulate a School Strategy Plan, the YAPIN Kertasemaya High School strategy plan which is written in the Curriculum Guidebook is written to become a school that has a depth of knowledge through managing libraries and multimedia rooms through deepening literacy activities. Furthermore, SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya makes literacy activities by including it in learning activities, which is 15 minutes before the first hour of learning begins.

The strategic plan refers to the considerations of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 21 of 2015 concerning the School Literacy Movement and the Indramayu Regional Regulation No. 3 of 2018 concerning the Indramayu Reading Development Movement. The achievement of becoming a literate school is expected to be realized in 2025.

In the operational plan of SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya which is written in its curriculum book related to literacy activities, namely "To realize a literacy school in 2025, SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya will carry out several activities as follows: 1) Carry out deliberation with foundations, teachers, committees and parents for carrying out reading activities in classrooms, libraries, multimedia rooms and at home; 2) prepare a budget for literacy activities in the form of procurement of reading books, improvement of multimedia room facilities, giving awards for teachers and students who are diligent in carrying out literacy activities; 3) have a representative library space; 4) participate in poetry reading, drama, writing competitions held by the government and universities.

b. Organizing the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) at SMA YAPIM Kertasemaya Indramayu

Based on data obtained from observations, interviews and document studies (meeting minutes) in SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya, after carrying out the process of preparing the Vision, Mission, Objectives and Strategies, and Operational Plans. The principal of SMA YAPIN Kertasemaya, through the deliberations of the teacher council and staff, discussed the determination of existing resources in the school environment to support the School Literacy Movement (GLS) program, including the determination of funding. To realize these activities, the principal formed a school literacy team. The formation of the literacy team was confirmed in the Decree of the School Literacy Team, the SK data that the researchers got from 2019 to 2022 with the SK number as follows: SK of the 2019 School Literacy Team, Number. 421.7/050/SMA.02.050/KM/VI/2019, Decree of the 2020 School Literacy Team, Number. 421.7/043/SMA.02.050/KM/VI/2020, Decree of the 2021 School Literacy Team, Number. 421.7/046/SMA.02.050/KM/VI/2021, Decree of the 2022 School Literacy Team, Number. 421.7/039/SMA.02.050/KM/VI/2022 .

The school library is designated as the center for school literacy activities after considering the resources available in the school library, such as library rooms, textbook librarians, reference books, magazines, which are used as sources of information media based on literacy culture.

c. Implementation of the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) at SMA YAPIM Kertasemaya Indramayu

The first step in implementing the School Literacy Movement began with the socialization of the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) in the internal school environment such as teachers, librarians, students to equalize perceptions about the GLS program as an effort to improve the reading literacy skills of YAPIN SMA students, through meetings, installation pamphlets in every corner of the classroom, pasted on school wall magazines including at the school entrance gate. The School Literacy Movement Program Task Force (GLS) conducts simulations or program pre-conditions to ensure that all GLS program plans can be implemented according to plan. This simulation involves all elements in the school environment including School Supervisors, School Committees, Principals, Teachers and students who are guided by a team of facilitators.

The principal who is in charge of the program, mobilizes all school elements to work according to their duties and functions, by building effective and efficient internal communication through official and unofficial channels. In addition, the Principal together with the literacy team make regular visits to each class at least once per semester in the form of an activity called one day literat to ensure the running of the School Literacy Movement program regarding the obligation to read 15 minutes before learning, granting permission for literacy activities in the library and multimedia rooms, and the YAPIN Literate Scientific Creation Center extracurricular is running effectively, holding a short story writing competition for the junior high school level. The Principal provides motivation to all teachers, staff and students in implementing the School Literacy Movement Program, through a persuasive communication approach and regularly holding dialogues with teachers and students related to program implementation. An equally important aspect that is carried out by the Principal is controlling all work units in the YAPIN SMA environment to ensure all work units work effectively, efficiently and accountably in the context of implementing the School Literacy Movement (GLS) program.

d. Evaluation of the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) at SMA YAPIM Kertasemaya Indramayu

Referring to the Strategic Plan of SMA YAPIM Kertasemaya Indramayu, that every school program must be evaluated in order to determine the success of school program performance, as well as the School Literacy Movement Program (GLS) the Principal conducts periodic evaluations every semester and yearly. Aspects that are evaluated are in the form of input, process, and output from the program, based on the results of the monitoring instrument and program evaluation conducted by the Quality Audit team from the Internal Quality Assurance System unit of YAPIN SMA.

Conclusion

The Principal's Leadership in Fostering a Literacy Culture of High School Students in Indramayu Regency, has been going quite well, in accordance with management rules that

begin with planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating, but has not shown comprehensive performance, because the level of understanding of the School Literacy Movement program has not equally. Other aspects that become obstacles include librarians who are not yet professional, the availability of library collections is not complete, and the corner of the reading room is not comfortable, funding needs to be increased.

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